

BER estimation for STBC-MC-DS-CDMA-4 antennas system by varied wavelet-carriers features via AWGN-flat channels

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ABSTRACT

This paper improves the bit error rate (BER) of the modern communication system by taking into account the effect of the wavelet shape and the number of carriers on the performance of the space time block code multi-carrier direct sequence code division multiple access (STBC-MC-DS-CDMA). Here the transmitter is moved with speeds 2 km/hr, 45 km/hr and 100 km/hr via Rayleigh flat fading channel. Here, 2 antennas are employed at the receiver to mitigate the multipath signal influence. The system's orthogonal frequencies are generated using Haar, Daubechies 4, Symlets 4, Cohen-Daubechies-Feauveau 1.1 with 9.7 and B-spline 3. The number of used carriers is 128, 512, and 1,024. Quadrature phase shift key (QPSK) is used with cyclic prefix 1/16 and a bandwidth of 20 MHz. traditional fast fourier transform (FFT) system is compared to the proposed discrete wavelet packet transform (DWPT) to show the BER enhancements. The space-time block coding (STBC) is used to enhance system capability in error correction. The proposed system shows significant improvement in BER, so that, it reaches to the same BER when using FFT but with less signal to noise ratio (SNR), which interns reduce the power consumed within the system and the cost.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The recent advancements in data network gave rise to many applications that are involved with almost every aspect of life ranging from top secret military operation to merely sending greetings for a birthday [1], [2]. These networks are becoming the backbone of societies because people are relying on them to spread news all over the world [3]–[5]. Even the elections consider social networks as a reliable source of information to study the citizen's point of views regarding a certain party or a candidate. Presently, these networks are growing to be self-sustained economic systems and a pillar of modern societies [6], [7].

To satisfy the higher bandwidths, the engineers could follow the traditional way by providing the extra bandwidths for the networks. Although this might be satisfactory it suffers from by unavoidable limitations. First limitation is the scares affordable free bandwidth because the radio frequency (RF) spectrum is highly congested. The second limitation is the bandwidth over a wide range will increase the influence of nonlinearity and deformations effect on the transmitted signals [8]–[11]. Different approaches will be invented to modulate the data that used narrower bandwidth with higher data rates, like the multi-carrier transmission (MC) or its modern version the orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) [12], [13].

Khan *et al.* [14] suggested a system of using discrete wavelet packet transform (DWPT) in OFDM instead of discrete fourier transform (DFT), then compared the performance between them based on bit error rate (BER) values and their corresponding signal to noise ratio (SNR), while Soni *et al.* [15], used a discrete wavelet transform (DWT) instead of fast fourier transform (FFT) in the OFDM system and test the proposed system by sending various images through different channels. They found that, the DWT is more reliable and has less SNR as compared to FFT. The use of these techniques is very important in many application as Roy *et al.* [16] depicts in his paper, so that a comparison is made between the FFT, discrete cosine transform (DCT), DWT and wals-hadamard transform (WHT) in many applications like electrocardiogram and photo-plethysmography signals. This paper aims to improve the BER of the code division multiple access (CDMA) multicarrier system by adding a DWPT instead of FFT as a suggestion to the system. Here the effected thing is reducing the SNR of the proposed system so that it reaches to the same BER but with low power, which consequently reduce the complexity and cost.

2. MC AND OFDM SYSTEMS

The idea of OFDM is based on dividing high bit rate stream of data into low bit stream segments. These segments are then modulated using orthogonal subcarriers to ensure neither overlapping between adjacent. These sub-streams are then combined together and transmitted using a main carrier before transmission. The block diagram of typical OFDM system is shown in Figure 1. Due to the fact that the resultant subs-terms have low rate with a low bandwidth requirement, then the OFDM requires less channel compared with the classical system. The fact that the subcarriers are orthogonal also allows the channels to overlap without interference because the orthogonality ensures complete separation among channels [12]. The carriers and pilots illustration are shown in Figure 2, so that, Figure 2(a) depicts the user and pilot subcarriers and how the packets are performed, while Figure 2(b) states the effect of orthogonality on the subcarrier [13].

Figure 1. OFDM block diagram

Consider a multi-carrier (MC) OFDM system with N subcarriers and each subcarrier f_k is used to modulate s_k sub-frame, then $s(t)$ transmitted signal is (1):

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=1}^N s_k \exp(j2\pi k f_k t) \tag{1}$$

Here f_k is equally spaced subcarriers and $f_k = BW/N$, BW is the bandwidth.

Let T to be $2/BW$, then according to Nyquist theorem each sample occurs at $T/2$ or $1/BW$. Therefore, any sub-stream subcarrier will exist at time mT then (1) becomes:

$$s(mT) = \sum_{k=1}^N s_k \exp\left(j2\pi \frac{km}{N}\right) \tag{2}$$

In (2) is exactly the inverse discrete fourier transform (IDFT) or inverse fast fourier transform (IFFT). At the receiver, an FFT circuit can be used to retrieve the transmitted signals from the incoming samples. This is quite clear from Figure 1, where the symbols are modulated, possibly using quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) [13].

Figure 2. OFDM idea; (a) the subcarriers assignment to users with pilot carriers and (b) OFDM signal spectrum

3. DISCRETE WAVELET PACKET TRANSFORM DWPT

In (2) can be viewed as a running filter with coefficients $\exp\left(j2\pi\frac{km}{N}\right)$ or in other words a low pass filter bank. The frequency location for each subcarrier f_k occurs at every $2^k \times f_0$, where f_0 is the fundamental frequency and f_k are its harmonics. This means that the power spectral density (PSD) will be widely spread over the channel as the sinusoidal functions extends from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. This consequently reduces the system spectral efficiency. In order to solve this problem, the analyzing function $\exp\left(j2\pi\frac{km}{N}\right)$ can be replaced by a more compact or spectral efficient function to ensure higher PSD concentration [14]. The DWT can ensure the achievement of this goal. Hence; by replacing DFT or FFT with DWT, the spectral efficiency can be increased due to time limited period of DWT functions resulting in a more reliable and higher signal quality [15], [16]. The wavelets are orthonormal functions such that [17], [18]:

$$\langle \Psi_l(t), \Psi_k(t) \rangle = \int \Psi_l(t) \Psi_k(t) dt = \begin{cases} 1 & l = k \\ 0 & l \neq k \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where $\Psi(t)$ is the mother wavelet, and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is inner product. The p vanishing moments can be found as (4):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^k \Psi(t) dt = 0 \text{ for } 0 \leq k < p \quad (4)$$

The vanishing moments describe the speed of decay of the wavelet function. So, the DWT output is:

$$X_{\Psi}(s, r) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \Psi_{t,r}(t) dt \quad (5)$$

Where s, r is the scale and translation. This means that the wavelet can capture the details of $x(t)$ in both time and frequency unlike FFT, which focuses only on the frequency domain. The translation means the wavelet is shifted in time while the scale is related to the width of the finite wavelet function. The scale and translation are shown in Figure 3 [19]. Assume an S samples discrete signal $x[n](n = 0, 1, \dots, S - 1)$ want to apply first level DWT to it, then:

$$y[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k]G_0[2n - k] + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k]G_1[2n - k] = y_{low}[n] + y_{high}[n] \tag{6}$$

Figure 3. The scale and translation of wavelet

In (6), the y_{low} is the signal coming from the low pass filter (LPF) bank with its impulse response $G_0[2n - k]$, while, y_{high} is the signal coming from the high pass filter (HPF) bank with its impulse response $G_1[2n - k]$. It is noted that the out coming signal has double the sampling rate n as the input signal. Thus, a decimation circuit by 2 ($\downarrow 2$) is required to switch back to the original sampling rate. Figure 4 shows the filter bank of the multi-level DWT [20]. The DWT functions G_0 and G_1 suggest that the incoming signal will be transformed to orthogonal frequencies in the rate of $\frac{f}{2^k}$ where $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ which is the number of analysis levels. The reconstruction functions H_0 and H_1 are the inverse for the analyzing functions G_0 and G_1 . In reconstruction filter, the sampling rate is up by a factor of 2 ($\uparrow 2$) to reverse the decimation process. The DWT can be modified to be identical to FFT and further increases the final signal PSD concentration. The modification comes from decomposing y_{high}^1 in the same manner y_{low}^1 at every stage. This analysis is called DWPT. The filters used for DWPT is shown in Figure 5 [21], [22].

Figure 4. Filter banks and LPF response

Figure 5. DWPT analysis filter

To generate the orthonormal subcarriers by using inverse discrete wavelet packet transform (IDWPT), consider (6) and by using mallat’s pyramid algorithm (MPA) for multi-resolution analysis (MRA), in (6) can be written as (7), so that $g(k)$ is called the wavelet coefficient function and is related to $h(\cdot)$ (10). Then for a scaling function of order N , in (11) can be depicted. In addition, the dilation and wavelet equations can be written as seen in (12) and (13):

$$y(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} a_{j_0}(k)\Phi_{j_0}(t - k) + \sum_{j=j_0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} b_j(k)\Psi_j(2^m t - k) \tag{7}$$

$$a_j(k) = \sum_m h(m - 2k)a_{j+1}(m) \tag{8}$$

$$b_j(k) = \sum_m g(m - 2k)b_{j+1}(m) \tag{9}$$

$$g(k) = (-1)^k h(1 - k) \tag{10}$$

$$g(k) = (-1)^k h(N - 1 - k) \tag{11}$$

$$\Phi(t) = \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} h(k)\Phi(2t - k) \tag{12}$$

$$\Psi(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (-1)^k h(k)\Phi(2t + k - N + 1) \tag{13}$$

Therefore, by using MPA and extending it to the DWPT, series of $x[n]$ vector can be analyzed using the following transformation matrix for L number of stages [23], [24].

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} h(0) & h(1) & h(2) & h(3) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h(0) & h(1) & h(2) & h(3) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ h(4) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & h(0) & h(1) & h(2) & h(3) \\ h(2) & h(3) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(0) & h(1) \\ g(0) & g(1) & g(2) & g(3) & \dots & g(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & g(0) & g(1) & g(2) & g(3) & \dots & g(L-1) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ g(4) & \dots & g(0) & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & g(0) & g(1) & g(2) & g(3) \\ g(2) & g(3) & \dots & g(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & g(0) & g(1) \end{bmatrix} \tag{14}$$

By substituting (11) in (14), the transformation matrix becomes:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} h(0) & h(1) & h(2) & h(3) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h(0) & h(1) & h(2) & h(3) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ h(4) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(0) & h(1) & h(2) & h(3) \\ h(2) & h(3) & \dots & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(0) & h(1) \\ h(L-1) & -h(L-2) & h(L-3) & \dots & h(1) & -h(0) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h(L-1) & -h(L-2) & h(L-3) & \dots & h(1) & -h(0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ h(L-5) & \dots & h(0) & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(L-1) & -h(L-2) & h(L-3) & -h(L-4) \\ h(L-3) & \dots & h(1) & -h(0) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(L-1) & -h(L-2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Using the orthonormal property, the reconstruction matrix is simply the transpose of the analysis function. Hence, at the construction side the following matrix is used (16):

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} h(0) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(2) & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & 0 & h(1) \\ h(1) & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \vdots & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h(0) \\ \vdots & h(0) & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & h(L-1) & h(1) & h(L-1) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ h(L-1) & h(1) & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h(0) & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \vdots & h(0) & \dots & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & h(1) & h(1) & \vdots & 0 \\ 0 & h(L-1) & h(1) & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h(0) & \vdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \vdots & \dots & 0 & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h(1) & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & h(L-1) & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & h(0) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \vdots & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \vdots & 0 & \dots & h(0) & 0 & \vdots & \vdots & 0 & 0 & h(L-1) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \vdots & \dots & h(1) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \vdots & \vdots & h(L-1) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \vdots & h(0) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h(1) & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & h(L-1) & h(1) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & h(0) & h(2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

4. OFDM AND CDMA SYSTEMS

The OFDM can ensure a complete separation for overlapped channels due to the orthogonality property. This property is tightly adhered to the location of subcarriers. If the location of these subcarriers are dispositioned, then the orthogonality will fall apart and the system will experience the inter channel interference (ICI) [24]. The ICI will reduce the system performance due to the decrease in the signal quality. Therefore, certain modifications should be taken, and one of them is using CDMA [25]. The CDMA is built upon the spread spectrum system (SSS) technology by which it allows all the users to use the channel all the time. A typical CDMA is shown in Figure 6 [26]. In the CDMA, each user is assigned by a pseudo noise-sequence (PN-sequence). The word pseudo comes from the fact that the sequence will repeat itself after a period of time depending on the linear feedback shift register (LFSR) constraint length. The generated PN pulses are almost random. The auto correlation function (ACF) of the PN sequence has the property given in (17) [27].

$$ACF(t) = \int PN(t)PN(t+\tau)d\tau = \begin{cases} 1 & \tau = 0 \\ -\frac{1}{N} & \tau \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Where N is the maximal length and equals to 2^n-1 and n is the LFSR constraint length.

When the PN sequence is aligned with itself then the ACF will have 1 value otherwise the sequence will cancel the incoming data. Unfortunately, the PN-sequence has poor cross correlation function (CCF), so gold code is used. If the sequences are chosen carefully, then the CCF will have only three states, which are:

$$\left\{ \frac{-t(n)}{N}, -\frac{1}{N}, \frac{t(n)-2}{N} \right\} t(n) = \begin{cases} 1 + 2^{\frac{n+1}{2}} & \text{for } n \text{ odd} \\ 1 + 2^{\frac{n+2}{2}} & \text{for } n \text{ even} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

At the receiver side, the incoming streams are multiplied by the same gold code, then passed through a coherent detector as seen in Figure 7 [26]–[28]. Let the transmitted OFDM signal to be $s(t)$, then the received signal $y(t)$ is seen in (19):

$$y(t) = s(t)\check{c}(t) + N(t) \quad (19)$$

where $\check{c}(t)$ is the spreading code at the transmitter side, $N(t)$ is the impairments from the channel like noise or jamming or interference or multipath.

$$N(t) = n(t) + J(t) + \sum_{i=1}^M s(t - \tau_i)\check{c}(t - \tau_i) \tag{20}$$

Figure 6. A typical CDMA system block diagram

Figure 7. A detailed spread spectrum demodulator

Where $n(t)$ is the additive wide gaussian noise (AWGN), $J(t)$ is the jamming signal, τ is the time delay due to multipath and M is the number of multipath signals. After multiplying $y(t)$ by $c(t)$ then output signal $b(t)$ of the coherent detector for the input $s(t)$ is:

$$b(t) = \frac{1}{T_s} \left[\int_0^{T_s} s(t)\check{c}(t)c(t)dt + \int_0^{T_s} N(t)c(t)dt \right] \tag{21}$$

5. FREQUENCY FLAT FADING CHANNEL AND SPACE TIME BLOCK CODING

The practical channels are usually imperfect and thus are described using its impulse response. assume a frequency selective fading channel is h of length L then the received signal $r(t)$ is given in (22) [29]:

$$r(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} h(k)s(n - k) \tag{22}$$

Where $s(n)$ is the transmitted signal, in (22) shows that the channel with such channel impulse response (CIR) which will cause inter-symbols interference (ISI) or in the case of OFDM will be worse which is inter-block interference (IBI) or ICI. One of the methods that used to overcome the fading effect is the multiple-input and multiple-output (MIMO)-space time block coding (STBC) [30]. MIMO is a technique by which the symbol is transmitted through different paths in order to null the CIR. Here Alamouti's STBC is used to avoid the continuous need to update the CIR [31].

The simplest form of Alamouti scheme is the multiple-input single-output (MISO) of 1×2 which means that the number of receiving antennas is 1 and the transmitting antennas is 2 as in Figure 8. Let two symbols x_1 and x_2 to be transmitted by this MISO over two channels of CIR or sometimes called channel state information (CSI) of h_1 and h_2 , then the received symbols are:

$$y_1(t) = [h_1 \quad h_2] \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} + n_1(t) \quad (23)$$

Figure 8. A 2×1 single input multiple output (SIMO) system

At the second instance, the first antenna will transmit $x_2^*(t)$ and the second antenna will transmit $-x_1^*(t)$, so the received symbols at the second instance are:

$$y_2(t) = [h_1 \quad h_2] \begin{bmatrix} x_2^* \\ -x_1^* \end{bmatrix} + n_2(t) \quad (24)$$

Taking the conjugate of (24) and arranging the result to look like:

$$y_2^*(t) = [-h_2^* \quad h_1^*] \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} + n_2^*(t) \quad (25)$$

Where $n_1(t)$ and $n_2(t)$ are the AWGN in the first and second transmission instances respectively. Combining (24) with (25), then it can be shown that:

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1(t) \\ y_2^*(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 & h_2 \\ -h_2^* & h_1^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1(t) \\ x_2(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} n_1(t) \\ n_2^*(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$\text{Let } Y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1(t) \\ y_2^*(t) \end{bmatrix}, C_1 = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 \\ -h_2^* \end{bmatrix}, C_2 = \begin{bmatrix} h_2 \\ h_1^* \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } N = \begin{bmatrix} n_1(t) \\ n_2^*(t) \end{bmatrix} \text{ then } Y = [C_1 \quad C_2] \begin{bmatrix} x_1(t) \\ x_2(t) \end{bmatrix} + N$$

Here, the Alamouti orthogonal space time block code (OSTBC) can be extended from MISO to MIMO easily [32], [33]. H_1 and H_3 is depicted in (27) and so on for H_4 .

$$H_1 = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 & h_2 \\ -h_2^* & h_1^* \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } H_3 = \begin{bmatrix} H_1 & H_2 \\ -H_2^* & H_1^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The suggested system combines all the above concepts and integrate them into a single communication system as shown in Figure 9. First, the signals are mapped using quadrature phase shift key (QPSK) scheme. An OSTBC is added then the resultant stream is fed to IDWPT section to generate the orthogonal subcarriers. These pilots are used for synchronization and estimating the CSI of the channel in order to provide the necessary equalization if needed. This serial stream is then fed to a MIMO of 2×2 antennas then send over the channel.

The transmitter is assumed to be a mobile travelling at speeds 2 km/hr, 45 km/hr, and 100 km/hr creating maximum doppler shift (MDS) of 10.7 Hz, 241.7 Hz, and 537 Hz respectively. The channel is flat fading rayleigh channel with AWGN. The number of transmitted bits per test is (102,400 bits) coming from (100 packet*64 characters *16 bit/char). The OFDM physical layer settings are shown in Table 1.

Figure 9. The complete suggested communication system

Table 1. OFDM physical layer simulation settings

Parameter	Mobile MC-DS-CDMA	Scalable OFDMA-PHY
FFT or DWT size	128	2048
Number of used data subcarriers	64	720
Modulation types	QPSK	
Cyclic prefix	1/16	
Channel bandwidth (MHz)	20	20

Here, the mother wavelets utilized are as follows: Haar, Daubechies=db4, Symlets=sym4, Cohen-Daubechies-Feauveau=cdf, and B-spline 3=bs3. The results are as follows:

- a. MDS 10.7 Hz, the BER are shown in Figure 10 (see in Appendix)
- b. MDS 241.7 Hz, the BER are shown in Figure 11(see in Appendix)
- c. MDS 537 Hz, the BER are shown in Figure 12 (see in Appendix)

From Figure 10, it can be seen that to obtain a 10^{-3} BER, the SNR must be at least 28 db, while by using the proposed system it decreased to about 5 dB when using 512 subcarriers, and so on for the others. The percentage improvement is about 80 percent, which is very good. The big difference between the results of the proposed system and the traditional method beyond to the excellent orthogonality of DWPT over FFT, which reduces the effect of ICI and ISI on the transmitted data.

A comparison is made when motor driven systems (MDS) equal to 10.7 Hz [30], they reach to 10^{-3} BER (128 subcarrier) at 8 dB SNR in AWGN, while the proposed system reaches the same value at 5 dB. In addition, Ali *et al.* [34] for the same sub carrier reaches to 7 dB SNR, while at 1,024 subcarriers the SNR is 8 dB and the proposed system of this work gives 7 dB. In the same context, Kusumawardhana *et al.* [35] obtain SNR of about 7.5 dB over AWGN channel when using a multi-level coding CDMA. This comparison gives the preference of the proposed system over different algorithms used to enhance the BER evaluation.

7. CONCLUSION

Here, IDWPT/DWPT has an excellent performance as compared to the IFFT/FFT in all tests. This justifies the assumption that the DWPT has higher concentrated signal PSD. But in all cases, the BER increases with the increase of bit rate and this event is inevitable. The doppler shift has high impact on system performance as it increases due to the motion of the mobile station. The doppler shift changes the locations of the orthogonal subcarriers which derifts the orthogonality that depends on the difference between adjacent subcarriers, although, the pilots were transmitted to resynchronize the system but even at certain bit rate and motion speed they lose their effectiveness. Neither the STBC nor the CDMA are now able to track and fight of the doppler shift effect. It is highly noticed that the wavelets have no close relation to the bit rate and inspite of that, there are some kinds of wavelets that gives the worst performance upon FFT like bs3. Therefore, the wavelet selection should be carefully done.

APPENDIX

Figure 10. BER performance of STBC DWT-mobile MC-DS-CDMA in AWGN-flat fading channel with 128, 512, and 1,024 subcarriers respectively

Figure 11. BER performance of STBC DWT-mobile MC-DS-CDMA in AWGN-flat channel with 128, 512, and 1,024 subcarriers respectively

Figure 12. BER performance of STBC DWT-mobile MC-DS-CDMA in AWGN-flat channel with 128, 512, and 1,024 subcarriers respectively

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